

however, that none of the benomyl treatments controlled the nematode (Table 1). In the second experiment, *D. angustus* numbers were significantly lower in benomyl-treated plots than in

untreated plots at both sampling times (Table 2). Benomyl, however, failed to control the nematode effectively and nematode counts per stem remained high. ■

Table 1. Number of *D. angustus*/hill observed at rice crop maturity after benomyl treatments. Long Thanh My, Thu Duc district, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam.

Treatment	<i>D. angustus</i> /hill ^a (no.)
T1 Untreated	7.6 a ^b
T2 Seed treatment by soaking for 24 h in a solution of benomyl at 0.1% ai	8.4 a
T3 T2 + spraying at 30 DT ^c with a solution of benomyl at 0.1 ai at a rate of 400 dm ³ /ha	26.6 a
T4 Seedling treatment by spraying with a solution of benomyl at 0.1 ai 2 d before transplanting at a rate of 240 dm ³ /ha	10.7 a
T5 T4 + spraying at 30 DT with a solution of benomyl at 0.1 ai at a rate of 400 dm ³ /ha	2.6 a
T6 Spraying at 30 DT with a solution of benomyl at 0.1 ai at a rate of 400 dm ³ /ha	17 a
T7 T6 + spraying at flowering with a solution of benomyl at 0.1 ai at a rate of 500 dm ³ /ha	4.2 a
T8 Spraying at 21 d after flooding with a solution of benomyl at 0.1 ai at a rate of 400 dm ³ /ha	29.7 a
T9 Spraying at flowering with a solution of benomyl at 0.1 ai at a rate of 500 dm ³ /ha	11.5 a

^aMean of 4 replications. ^bMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^cDays after transplanting.

Table 2. Number of *D. angustus* observed/stem before and after spraying benomyl at two concentrations 40 d after sowing. Dong Phu, Chau Thanh district, Can Tho Province, Vietnam.

Treatment	<i>D. angustus</i> /stem ^a (no.)		
	1 d before treatment	10 d after treatment	20 d after treatment
Control (no benomyl spray)	33 a	83 a	64 a
Benomyl 0.1% ai	30 a	45 b	44 b
Benomyl 0.2% ai	32 a	42 b	43 b

^aMean of 4 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

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Water management

Water management in transplanted wetland rice

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We studied how water management practices affect grain yield and water use efficiency of transplanted rabi (winter) rice. We studied the response of rice crops subjected to various irrigation schedules and determined the most productive schedule when water is a limiting factor.

The experiment was laid out in a completely randomized design during 1989-91. No rain fell during the experiment. Thirty-day-old seedlings of Tellahamsa (120 d) were transplanted into 30-m² plots at Agricultural College Farm, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad. Soil was a clay loam. We applied 100:17.6:24.9 kg NPK/ha in three splits: 1/3 at transplanting, 1/3 at maximum tillering, and 1/3 at panicle initiation. Granulated butachlor (at 1.5 kg ai/ha) mixed with fine sand was applied at 4 d after transplanting (DT) and followed by handweeding at 30-35 DT.

Maintaining 5 cm of water yielded the most rice (5.5 t/ha) in the experiment but required 1,530 mm of the water. Applying 5 cm of water at 2 d after disappearance of ponded water (DADPW) did not reduce yield significantly, but it saved considerable water. 2 DADPW had the highest water use efficiency (5.41 kg grain/ha-mm) among treatments. Other treatments consumed less water than continuous submergence but yielded significantly less (see table). Severe cracks developed in these treatments and water stress occurred during and after panicle initiation. ■

Water regime	Grain yield (t/ha)	Water requirement (mm)	Water use efficiency (kg grain/ha-mm)
Continuous submergence (5 cm water)	5.5	1530	3.60
5 cm water 2 DADPW ^b	5.2	935	5.41
5 cm water 3 DADPW	4.6	850	5.37
5 cm water 4 DADPW	4.1	765	5.36
5 cm water 5 DADPW	3.4	680	4.95
LSD (0.05)	0.7	-	-

*Mean of 2 yr. ^bDADPW = d after disappearance of ponded water.

Farming systems

Establishing rainfed no-till winter crops under NPK fertilization after transplanted wet rice

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We studied the feasibility of establishing crops after transplanted wet rice during winter without tilling and using only residual moisture.

The field experiment was laid out in a factorial randomized block design, replicated four times, and conducted during winter seasons (1990-91 and 1991-92) at the University Farm, Kalyani, West Bengal, India. Experimental soil was a low-lying alluvial with 0.62% organic C, 0.06% total N, 7.9 kg available P/ha, 151.1 kg available K/ha, and pH 6.8.

Effect of different NPK fertilizer levels on seed and stover yields (t/ha) of rainfed winter crops of mustard, grasspea, lentil, and linseed after transplanted wet rice (IR36). West Bengal, India, 1990-92.

Rainfed winter crop	NPK fertilizer							
	None		Recommended dose		1.5 × recommended dose		Mean	
	Seed	Stover	Seed	Stover	Seed	Stover	Seed	Stover
Mustard	0.5	2.0	0.7	3.0	1.5	4.2	0.9	3.2
Grasspea	1.0	4.0	1.1	4.9	0.8	4.4	1.0	4.4
Lentil	1.2	4.7	1.3	4.0	1.2	3.7	1.2	4.1
Linseed	0.4	1.3	0.7	1.6	0.8	1.8	0.6	1.5
Mean	0.8	3.0	1.0	3.4	1.1	3.5	0.9	3.3
	Fertilizer (F)		Crops (C)		F × C			
	Seed	Stover	Seed	Stover	Seed	Stover	Seed	Stover
LSD (0.05)			0.3	ns ^a	0.4	0.7	0.5	1.2

^ans = not significant.

Varietal diffusion in a rice farming system

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We studied the diffusion pattern of rice varieties developed through a farming systems research and extension (FSR/E) program. Farmers in the southern Sri Lankan district of Matara are confronted with strong soil acidification (pH 3.5-4.0) during the dry season (DS) and excess water during the wet season (WS).

During the technology generation stage of the FSR/E program, rice varieties were screened for tolerance for soil acidification and submergence. Varieties BW272-3 and At85-1 were selected. Both have growth duration of 3 1/2 mo. Based on experimental and on-farm trial results, BW272-3 was introduced in the district in 1988 DS and At85-1 in 1990 DS. See figure for diffusion trends.

BW272-3 had medium tolerance for acidic soils and submerged condition. It exhibited medium resistance to thrips (*Thrips oryzae*) and sheath blight (ShB) (*Corticium sasakii*) and is 95-100 cm tall. The field's microenvironment did not favor the spread of common insect pests and diseases. Unfavorable characteristics included low resistance to brown planthopper (*Nilaparvata lugens* Stål), high grain shattering, lower grain weight (21-22 g/1,000 seeds), and white pericarp.

BW272-3 was considered to be a moderately appropriate variety for the target area. Farmers adopted this variety at first, but later responded to the low grain weight and higher farmgate price of red-pericarped varieties. The diffusion curve of BW272-3 shows a declining adoption trend two seasons after it was introduced (see figure).

Red-pericarped At85-1 had medium tolerance for acidic soils, low shattering, and higher grain weight (25-26 g/1000 seeds). It had little tolerance for submerged condition and was susceptible to BPH, thrips, and ShB. Its short height (81-87 cm) made the microenvironment suitable for pests and diseases.

After eight seasons, farmers are again adopting BW272-3, which is moderately